

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE SKILLS IN FORMING THE COMPETENCE OF WORKING WITH INFORMATION IN SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes ideas about creativity, creative thinking of students, factors of development of their creative abilities, the general essence of the process of developing creative qualities in students.*

Keywords: *creativity, creativity, information technologies, creative thinking, innovation, competence.*

The problem of creativity of a modern person is becoming more urgent in all aspects of the continuing education system. A developing society needs creative, first of all, intellectual-creative, courageous, non-traditional and unique people who are able to think and solve problems effectively. Modern society needs creative individuals who are able to express themselves in various fields of activity. Today, creativity is an important criterion of a person and is considered a factor of his overall development. Therefore, special attention is paid to creativity, active creativity at the intellectual level in education policy.

In our country, as a result of consistent reforms aimed at creating conditions for a person, his all-round development and well-being, the realization of his interests, bringing the quality and efficiency of education to a new level, opportunities for the development of creative abilities of students are being created on the basis of interactive teaching methods. Educational scientists O. Jamoliddinova, O. Musurmonova, M. Urazova, N. Egamberdieva, E. Yuzlikaeva, Sh. Sharipov, A.O, Sh. specific aspects, social factors influencing the development of creativity qualities, the activity of the individual, as well as the creative content of the ways and forms of forming critical, creative thinking in students are highlighted.

American scientist J. Gilford shows a number of individual abilities that characterize creativity:

- fluency of thought;
- to be able to use the thought according to the purpose;
- uniqueness (originality);
- curiosity;
- the ability to create hypotheses;
- imagination, fantasy (fantasy).

The most important component in the structure of students' innovative activity is reflection. In order to fully understand the general nature of the process of developing creative qualities in a person, it is necessary to first understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity".

The systematic conduct of the educational process and activities aimed at developing the creative activity of students is of great importance in the development of their creative thinking and professional competence.

Competence is the manifestation of the student's theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and qualifications, worldview, faith and all personal individual social psychological qualities. One of the important factors ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education is the teacher's competence in his subject.

From the point of view of the problem-based method of education, the main direction in education is to solve educational problems, to form knowledge and creative thinking activities in students. In the process of education, new, increasingly complex continuous problems are organized. In such education, a whole lesson can be devoted to solving one main problem. Or the educational material to be studied during one lesson can be divided into a number of coherent problems. After the problems are solved one after the other, systematization and generalization of knowledge is carried out. Creative thinking serves to direct students' cognitive activities to a certain goal, adds creativity to the lesson, and ultimately creates favorable conditions for students' mental development. Research scientists recommend different ways to create problem situations. One of the ways to teach students to think creatively is the method of independent work. Creative work of students, which is widely used in every aspect of education, has been constantly in the focus of researchers' attention as a means of increasing the effectiveness of education. Research scientists have always advocated the wide use of creative works in the course of the lesson. Because students' acquisition of knowledge and teaching to think creatively, first of all, is formed in the process of performing creative work, finding solutions to the problems and issues in front of them. So, let's dwell on the question of what the students' creative works are.

They gave him different answers. For example, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor A. Ghulomov defines creative works as follows: "Creative works are first of all organized under the direct guidance of the teacher and aimed at strengthening the students' theoretical knowledge and improving their skills in information technologies. we understand active conscious activity that serves a specific purpose. For example, S. Matjonov: "...creative work is an integral part of education. Its distinctive feature is determined by the performance of educational tasks directly by the student, without the participation of the teacher, and is carried out mainly by working on information, it implies the effective use of additional resources.

According to Patti Drapeau, creative thinking is, first of all, comprehensive thinking about a specific issue. Multidisciplinary thinking requires students to rely on multiple ideas when completing learning assignments, problems, and tasks. In contrast, one-sided thinking is based on only one correct idea.

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental sharpness, "ensures active involvement of students in the educational process."

Creative thinking requires a student's self-confidence, activity and leadership, and the ability to take risks. Creativity depends on the following qualities: ingenuity, the ability to find solutions based on new thinking, the ability to look at a problem from different and new angles, interest in experience, the ability to think and constantly learn.

For the successful implementation of creativity in the educational process, it is recommended to use a combination of different types of creative tasks, methods and methods of their implementation.

Based on his work experience, the teacher tries to develop creative tasks aimed at developing the creative abilities of schoolchildren in the educational process.

The result of these tasks should be a high level of creative thinking, development of creative imagination, students should use innovative methods of creativity in the process of completing tasks.

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